

Physicochemical Studies and Hyperthermia Biomedical Modeling Application of Fe₃O₄ Magnetic Nanoclusters Coated with Barbituric Acid

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Abstract

A magnetic nano-clusters (Fe₃O₄) coated with barbituric acid and its complex were synthesized. The structure, mode of bonding, surface charge, physical size, and morphology of the prepared materials were studied. The mechanisms of the thermal decomposition for the naked Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticle (MNP), Coated NP, and the prepared complex were studied by thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA). The activation energy for the prepared compounds was determined. Thermal transitions and kinetic studies of the prepared materials were determined by differential scanning calorimetry technique (DSC). A model was designed using the 3D Slicer software platform and imported to Computer Simulation Technology (CST studio). The model was simulated in the presence of prepared nanoparticles: barbituric acid@ Fe₃O₄ to calculate the specific absorption rate (SAR) and thermal simulation of the model. The results indicate that the prepared MNP enhances both microwave imaging and hyperthermia treatment at low frequencies.

Keywords: Fe₃O₄, IR spectra, transmission electron microscopy (TME), thermal analysis, Magnetic Hyperthermia, and Computer simulation technology (CST).

1. Introduction

There is an immense interest in the development of new nanomaterials for the potential use of multifunctional applications in the biomedical field. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) have special properties that can overcome variant biomedical obstacles [1]. The MNPs have an important diagnostic imaging, delivery of thermal energy, and Magnetic Fluid Hyperthermia (MFH) which is a standalone therapy. These nanoparticles have a large surface area - volume ratio, that reduces the dose, improves the toxicity profile, and increases solubility. Their size allows them to penetrate the cell membrane, cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and reach the site of lesions easily. Despite numerous positive results from research using MNPs as a medicinal material, some issues remain [2, 3].

The most frequently used magnetic nanomaterial is the superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIOs), which contain magnetite (Fe₃O₄) with monodomain particles of size range 5–20 nm, characterized by high magnetic saturation, and high bio-compatibility. These particles become magnetized only when they are subjected to an external magnetic field; once the field is removed, they lose their magnetism. Due to their small size, SPIOs can

overcome the effect of the gravitational force, magnetic field gradient, and magnetic agglomeration. Moreover, these particles are used as a contrast agent in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for diagnostic purposes [4].

Surface-functionalized magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles are novel functional materials, which are widely used in biotechnology. The surface coatings affect MNPs by decreasing their aggregation, oxidation, and potential toxicity. These formulations of coated surface magnetite-based nanotherapeutics gained the USA Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval for human use. For the practical application to be implemented, the particles must have an interactive functional group on the surface. Moreover, the iron oxide NPs' surface could be modified by a variety of materials; organic or inorganic, such as polymers, biomolecules, metals, etc. In several cases, magnetite was utilized directly in therapeutic approaches and as a result, particles are identified by macrophages in the mononuclear phagocyte system and removed from the body [5]. The small nanoparticles have longer half-lives where they are captured by lymph nodes and give them a chance to do their tasks. The Nps penetrate the cancer cells and remain in the endosomes. Breakdown of magnetite causes oxidative stress by forming hydroxyl radicals (HO•) via the Fenton reaction. Particles have been encased to produce "stealth" particles, which increase biocompatibility, decrease toxicity, and ensure non-immunogenicity [6-5]. Developments are progressing towards additional clarification and complex multifunctional magnetic designs [7, 8]. The major challenge is the strategy of synthesis of iron oxide NPs surface functionalization. Recent breakthroughs in chemistry have enabled bioconjugated magnetic particles to be specifically targeted to cancer cells, allowing for the preservation of healthy tissue while killing cancer cells.

Hyperthermia is a medical treatment in which body tissue is exposed to high temperatures (42 °C -45°C) to damage and kill cancer cells. It has been studied extensively in both vitro and in vivo platforms. Clinical trials of hyperthermia have limitations such as acute necrosis, coagulation, or carbonization of the tissue. In clinical hyperthermia, thermoablation is mostly undesired. The challenge is to restrict heating to the tumor sites and to reduce the effect of heating due to the development of thermal tolerance in cells from the expression of heat shock proteins. So, there are two issues to be optimized: increase the temperature within the target region only (tumors) leaving all other regions unaffected and optimize the thermal homogeneity in the target volume. An effective cancer therapy is needed to overcome these obstacles, and the side effects of conventional therapies and combine several approaches to explore site-specific therapies [8-9].

Magnetic Fluid Hyperthermia (MFH) is a promising approach towards adjuvant cancer therapy that is based on localized heating of tumors using magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) and radiation sources to deliver heat to the cancer site. The tumor cells are radiation resistant as well as oxygen deficient. MFH makes tumor cells sensitive to radio-sensitization and nanoparticle therapy as tumor cells show toxicity to nanoparticles MFH. [10-9].

In this article, the art of combined use of hyperthermia by nanoparticles coated with barbituric acid is proven to have a great impact on public health as an alternative therapeutic oncology and monitoring therapy. These nanoparticles enhance the microwave imaging techniques and site-specific therapy of hyperthermia. Barbituric acid does not only act as an antitumor but is also utilized as an anesthetic agent.

2. Experimental Synthesis

Preparation of magnetic nanoparticle (MNP):

Iron oxide nanoparticle powder (Fe₃O₄) of size 10 nm was purchased from Nanotech Egypt. Magnetite nanoparticles have been synthesized via the co-precipitation method [11].

Synthesis of MNP surface modification with barbituric acid nanostructures:

0.01 gm of MNP was re-suspended in 10 ml water as a result of sonication. The ferrofluid solution was added to 0.1 gm of barbituric acid at 55°C using automatic rotation for 30 minutes followed by 15 minutes of hand shaking at room temperature. The mixture was then downsized by sonication using a bath-type sonicator at 42°C.

Synthesis of the Fe₃O₄ complex with barbituric acid (F₃O₄-Ba Complex):

A hot clear solution of 0.01 mole of Fe₃O₄ in 25 ml water was added to 0.01-mole solution of barbituric acid dissolved in 25 ml of hot ethanol for preparation. The reaction was done in the presence of 5 ml concentrated

ammonia solution. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 45 min and therefore the precipitated complexes were filtered, washed many times with water, and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 .

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM):

The morphology and the outer surface of barbituric acid @ Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and barbituric acid - Fe_3O_4 complex powders were examined by Scanning Electron Microscope (Jeol, JSM-6360LA, Japan).

Spectrophotometric measurements:

Nujol mull ultraviolet and visible spectra:

The solid complexes were measured by Perkin Elmer Lambda 4.B UVLVIS

Infrared spectra:

The data have been carried out by Shimadzu 4800s FTIR spectrometer Maxima, Japan, KBr dick technique.

Thermal analyses measurements:

The measurements have been carried out by Shimadzu DSC-60A Maxima, Japan, and Shimadzu TGA 50 GALM, Maxima, Japan, at nitrogen atmosphere, rate of heating $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

X-Ray Diffractometer:

The dried nanoparticles and barbituric acid were analyzed for their crystalline nature by X-ray diffractometer (Shimaduz, XRD- 7000, Maxima, Japan)

Zeta potential:

The surface charge of the nanoparticles was measured by Zetasizer (Nano ZS, Malvern Inst., Malvern. Worcestershire, UK).

Computer simulation technology (CST)

Finite Element Modeling (FEM)

3D model was designed using CST (Computer simulation technology) Studio which is a high-performance full-wave electromagnetic simulator for 3D volumetric modeling. It integrates simulation, visualization, solid modeling, and automation where the solution to 3D electromagnetic problems is obtained accurately. As well, it applies the Finite Element Method (FEM) which has been progressively used in studying tissue–electromagnetic field interactions because of its capability to solve the dynamics of physical phenomena in composite geometries^[12].

The model was comprised of tumor cells having a spherical shape with a total volume of 4.188mm^3 ($r = 1\text{mm}$.) inserted in a blood vessel of total volume 3.137cm^3 ($r=1\text{cm}$, $L=1\text{cm}$) and surrounded by barbituric acid@ Fe_3O_4 NPs. Nanoparticles were inserted to investigate their effect on enhancing microwave imaging and tumor treatment. [282 2, shows the nanoparticle distribution surrounding cancer cells during the simulation process. The dielectric and thermal properties of the tissues were assigned.

Thermal Simulation

The designed model was simulated by running the thermal transient solver in CST Studio. The temperature distribution at 915 MHz was calculated. Two temperature monitors were used to record temperature increments as the tissues were illuminated by the electromagnetic wave. One monitor was placed at the center of the tumor; the other monitor was placed at 5 mm away from the center of the tumor. We applied the hyperthermia treatment for 600 Sec (10 minutes).

Finally, the distribution of temperature along a horizontal axis passing through the center of cancer cells was computed to study the effect of the applied thermal energy on the healthy cells around the tumor.

3. Results and Discussion

Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM):

Typical nanostructures of prepared particles have been performed by TEM images. The TEM images of Fe_3O_4 (NP) coated with barbituric acid show uniformly dispersed nanoparticles of average diameter from 9-12nm associated with slight aggregation which confirms the presence of magnetite structure, while the TEM images of Fe_3O_4 –Ba complex confirm the synthesis of high quality, free, highly monodispersed nanoparticles with average size from 5-10 nm.

- Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM): The observation of SEM photographs of the dried barbituric acid with Fe_3O_4 NP demonstrated that most of the particles are completely spherical, Figure 1-a. The SEM photos of Fe_3O_4 – Ba complex, Figure 1-b, show that the synthesized complex has an octahedral configuration with high density.

Figure 1: SEM images of: (a) Fe_3O_4 (NP) coated with barbituric acid (b) Fe_3O_4 – Ba Complex

X-Ray Diffractometer:

The XRD diffraction pattern for Fe_3O_4 NPs showed many peaks at 2θ values of 30.154, 31.677, 35.524, 43.109, 45.31, 53.523, 57.046, 62.699, 70.865 and 74.844. The maximum peaks corroborate the presence of magnetite structure.

The crystallinity of barbituric acid is determined by X-ray diffraction and shows intense peaks of crystallinity. The 2θ peaks at 17.53, 19.765, 20.852, 22.231, 26.578, 29.231 and 30.743.

Structural characterization of barbituric acid @ Fe_3O_4 NPs has been performed using XRD analysis. The 2θ maximum peaks at 29.258, 30.154, 35.524, and 49.503. Since these peaks are small, the possibility of a magnetite structure cannot be completely excluded. In addition to these four peaks, there are unidentified peaks that appear in the XRD pattern.

The crystal structure of Fe_3O_4 – Ba Complex was investigated using XRD. The 2θ peaks at 10.012, 16.548, 32.354, and 28.532. The spectra exhibited less intense peaks compared to barbituric acid @ Fe_3O_4 NPs, which indicates that the obtained sample is mostly amorphous instead of crystalline nature. On comparing our XRD patterns, each component has its crystal region in the hybrid nanoparticles.

Zeta potential:

Z - Potential measurements were made for coated nanoparticles. Barbituric acid @ Fe_3O_4 NPs shows a decrease of the negative surface charge - 1.5 mV., while Fe_3O_4 – Ba complex shows a very low positive surface charge of 0.135 mV. Such low values suggest weak negative and positive charges at the surface of the nanoparticles, yielding low stability of nanoparticles due to weak electrostatic repulsive forces between carboxyl groups.

Infrared (IR):

1- The IR spectral data of the ligand, its metal complex, and Fe_3O_4 -coated NP are summarized in, Table 1. The strong bands are in the range of 3578 cm^{-1} for the symmetric and asymmetric (OH) stretching of the ligand, while the (NH) band appears at 3192 cm^{-1} . The sharp band at 1750 cm^{-1} was attributed to (C=O), whereas the band at 1610 cm^{-1} is for the (C=N). The information obtained suggested the existence of barbituric acid within the tautomeric forms.

2- A comparison of the IR spectra of the ligand, Fe_3O_4 – Ba Complex, and Fe_3O_4 coated NP, Table 1, brings out the subsequent facts.

The spectra of Fe_3O_4 – Ba Complex and Fe_3O_4 coated NP exhibited a broad band at $3500\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, that attributed to n OH of the associated water molecules, whereas the observed band at $860\text{--}740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ referred to coordinated water molecules [14]. The change in intensity and position of the carbonyl band indicate that at least one of the carbonyl groups of the barbituric acid was coordinated with the metal. The nNH band at 3178 cm^{-1} turned to a broad band at 3100 cm^{-1} within the Fe_3O_4 – Ba Complex suggesting that coordination bonds have been formed between the NH groups and the metal ion. The presence of n C=N and n C-O at 1650 and 1402 cm^{-1} , respectively, provides strong evidence that the ligand undergoes tautomerization to the enol structure before complexing with the metal ion

^[15]. Moreover, the weak bands observed at 536 and 449 cm^{-1} for the Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex confirm the formation of Fe –N and Fe –O bonds ^[16].

For F_3O_4 coated NP The absence of n C=N and n C-O bands indicates that there is no tautomerization and the ligand existed in the keto form when it is coated to the Fe_3O_4 Nanoparticle. The weak bands at 542 and 408 cm^{-1} respectively prove the formation of Fe –N and Fe –O bonds

Table 1: IR spectra (cm^{-1}) of barbituric acid (H_2L_2), Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex and F_3O_4 coated NP.

Barbituric acid	F_3O_4 coated NP	Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex	Assignment
3578	3464- 3238	3423	ν (as & sy) OH
3192	3100 (b)	3205(b)	ν NH
3095	2924,2859		ν OH
2874	2879(b)	2362	
1755-1710	1699(s)	1703 (b)	ν C=O
1610	-	1650-1607	ν C=N
1421-1354	1429	1428-1402	ν $\text{CH}_2\delta$ NH
1291,1244	1347	1347	ν (C–O), ν C=N
933	1091-1040	1292	δ O-H
	1092-1041	1095 (b)	ν (CN), ν CCH
781	784	771	coordinated (H_2O)
	542-509	536	ν Fe-N
	408	449	ν Fe-O

Nujol spectra:

Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex, gave bands at 319, 354, and 461 nm. These bands are because CT ($t_{2g} \rightarrow \pi^*$) and CT ($\pi \rightarrow e_g$) confirm the existence of Octahedral configuration ^[17,18].

Thermal studies: -

The TGA of naked Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles shows that it lost about 5% of its weight within the temperature range from 25 to 300°C due to the loss of residual water in the sample. On the other hand, for F_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with Barbituric acid, owing to the removal of absorbed water, the weight loss of the entire nanocomposite is slightly below 200°C. Then the barbituric acid began to decompose within the range from 183°C to 500°C and the weight loss was 72%. At higher temperatures (500 to 800°C), there is no significant weight loss and the remaining weight is 17% from the initial weight. From the previous study, it has been found that the ratio of barbituric acid to Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles is (15:2)^[19]

Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex, lost 4.685% of its weight below 191°C due to the removal of the inner and outer sphere water. Then the degradation of the complex began at 200°C and therefore the final temperature of decomposition is around 479°C

DSC technique is used to determine the thermal transitions of a compound like glass transition, melting, and crystallization. Plotting heat flow against temperature gave three regions. within the initial region, glass transition temperatures are often determined by taking the center of the incline, within the second region the crystallization is often determined by taking the temperature at the lowest point of the dip, and within the third region, melting temperatures are often determined by taking the temperature at the top of the peak ^[20]. The glass transition and crystallization temperatures have been determined from the DSC graph for the Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex and Fe_3O_4 coated NP, Table 2. The crystallization temperatures for Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex were 258.19 and 67.4 °C, 228.48 °C for F_3O_4 coated NP in which the compounds gained enough energy to be in order arrangements subsequently gave off heat through an exothermic transition.

Table 2: Thermal transitions of Fe₃O₄–Ba Complex and F₃O₄ coated NP.

Compound	Peak (type)	Tc (°C)	Tm (°C)	Tg (°C)	Enthalpy (ΔH) (J/g)
Fe ₃ O ₄ –Ba Complex	a(endo)	258.19	-----	270.33	-197.27
F ₃ O ₄ coated NP	a(endo)	67.41	-----	68.77	-79.63
	b(endo)	228.48	-----	224.66	-35.96

The Debye model is used to explain how the capacity changes over a wide temperature range [21]. The formula for Cp is expressed empirically:

$$C_p = aT + b \quad (1)$$

By plotting Cp against T, we can obtain a straight line, from which we can determine the "a" and "b" parameters from the slope and intercept of the line, as shown in Table 3.

The Debye model is also applied to complexes using subsequent equations for further applications:

$$\frac{C_p}{T} = xT^2 + \gamma \quad (2)$$

$$C_p \times C_v = xT^3 + \gamma T \quad (3)$$

The electronic and lattice heat capacity coefficients are denoted as γ and α , respectively. We assume Cp equals Cv, representing the heat capacity at constant volume. When plotting Cp / T against T², we observe straight lines with slopes α and intercepts γ , as shown in Table 4.

Table 3: The slopes "a" and intercept "b" for DSC curves of the compounds

compound	a ₁ [b ₁]	a ₂ [b ₂]	a ₃ [b ₃]	a ₄ [b ₄]	a ₅ [b ₅]	a ₆ [b ₆]	a ₇ [b ₇]
Fe-Ba complex	-0.347 [190.7]	0.988 [-522.57]	0.0575 [-8.833]	-0.0331 [46.384]	-0.4429 [-246.09]		-
	504-532 °K	536-551 °K	569-599 °K	619-651 °K	651-696 °K		
F ₃ O ₄ coated NP	0.009 [-0.0008]	0.0081 [0.0077]	0.0084 [-0.0009]	0.0148 [-0.06562]	0.013 [-0.0016]	0.0164 [-0.1109]	0.0268 [-0.0940]
	300-303 °K	303-338 °K	338-358 °K	350-463 °K	500-512 °K	540-631 °K	664-706 °K

Table 4: The slopes "α" and intercept "γ" for DSC curves of the compounds

Compound	α ₁ [γ ₁]	α ₂ [γ ₂]	α ₃ [γ ₃]	α ₄ [γ ₄]	α ₅ [γ ₅]	α ₆ [γ ₆]	α ₇ [γ ₇]
Fe ₃ O ₄ –Ba Complex	-0.0009 [0.0625]	-0.0054 [0.1643]	0.0231 [-0.6539]	0.0003 [-0.345]	0.0044 [-0.1501]		
	311-463 °K	483-536 °K	536-547 °K	559-599 °K	655-696 °K		
F ₃ O ₄ coated NP	-0.0275 [0.3339]	0.0512 [-522.57]	0.0014 [0.0577]	0.0029 [0.1371]	0.0283 [-0.54]	0.0025 [0.0115]	0.00109 [-0.3519]
	315-331 °K	338-344 °K	369-433 °K	463-484 °K	500-507 °K	552-611 °K	648-705 °K

- Determination of kinetic parameters from thermal degradation:

The thermo gravimetric data assessed the kinetic parameters of solid-state reactions involving weight loss or gain, as discussed in the references. Broido's technique, detailed in references [22], was employed to jointly evaluate the activation energy related to each stage of decomposition. The activation energy (Ea) for each stage was calculated using the following equation:

$$\ln \ln \left(\frac{1}{Y} \right) = \left(\frac{-E_a}{R} \right) \frac{1}{T} + \text{constant} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Where,} \quad Y = \frac{Wt - W_{\infty}}{W_0 - W_{\infty}} \quad (5)$$

Where Y is the fraction of the number of initial molecules that do not decomposed; Wt, W_{∞} and W_0 represent the weight at any time t, the weight at infinite, and the initial weight, respectively. By blotting $\ln \ln (1/Y)$ vs. $1/T$ a straight line was obtained and the activation energy could be evaluated from the slope.

The kinetic parameters of the Fe-Ba complex and F_3O_4 -coated NP are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Kinetic parameters of Fe_3O_4 –Ba Complex and F_3O_4 coated NP by Broido method

Compound	Decomposition Temperature range (°C)	Regression value (R^2)	Activation energy in Kcal/mol
Fe_3O_4–Ba Complex	190-279	0.809	6.705
	279-429	0.9929	22.655
F_3O_4 coated NP	24-84	0.757	69.033
	84-183	0.970	5.387
	183-261	0.978	9.523
	261-385	0.989	1.471
	385-503	0.947	12.518

Computer Simulation Technology (CST)

Dielectric properties at frequency 915 MHz, and thermal properties of the human tissues are shown in Table 7 [23]. The effect of microwave imaging using FEM for the designed 3D model was studied. Figure 2- a, indicates a localized region of the highest SAR value (yellow region) that coincides with the position of the inserted tumor cells at 915 MHz. SAR is determined by the “rate of temperature rise”.

The effect of MFH treatment at 915 MHz using FEM for the designed model was studied, Figures (2-b, 3), Show the presence of nanoparticles that cause an increase in the tumor’s temperature to exceed 42oC and are sufficient for hyperthermia treatment and destroy tumor cells. Also, the temperature outside the tumor is below 38oC which keeps the surrounding tissues healthy unharmed.

Figure 2: (a) SAR distribution and (b) Temperature distribution are computed by using the FEM after applying microwave input power at 915 MHz

Figure 3: Temperature distribution curve using the FEM thermal model during hyperthermia treatment for 10 minutes (inside tumor, outside tumor)

Figure 4: Temperature distribution curve as a function of distance.

Table 6. Dielectric properties and thermal properties at frequency 915 MHz

Thermal Properties	Conductivity σ	0.59 (S/m)
	Heat capacity C	3621 (J/kg. $^{\circ}$ C)
Dielectric Properties	Thermal conductivity K	0.5 (W/m. $^{\circ}$ C)
	Electrical permittivity ϵ_r	38.84 (F/m)

The relation between temperature and distance shows a localized high temperature at the center of the tumor (approximately 42 $^{\circ}$ C) and it decreases as moving away from the center of the tumor as shown in, Figure 4.

4. Conclusion

Fe₃O₄ –Ba Complex and Fe₃O₄ coated NP have different structures, types of bonds, morphology, and thermal behaviors. The use of magnetic nanoparticles in multimodal hyperthermia imaging and tumor treatment is a new

technique emerging in synthesis, targeting, energy deposition of nanoparticles, and temperature distribution in tissue. The nanoparticles allow better penetration power for biological tissues at lower frequencies.

The Iron oxide nanoparticles' half-lives are affected by particle size and coating. To guarantee optimal particle deposition on tumor cells, the coating is necessary to decrease rapid opsonization and macrophage phagocytosis. The advantage of this combination over other hyperthermia agents is that the desired maximum temperature can be easily reached and stabilized by adjusting the Fe₃O₄ composite Np and magnetic field strength. As a novel and more powerful way of cancer treatment, this composite allows for both diagnosis and medicine release. Magnetic core, surface coating, and functionalized outer coating are the three functional elements of the magnetic nanoparticle approach allowing for a less invasive and more effective treatment.

5. Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

6. Preprint:

<https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-4364432/v1>

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